

SHORT NOTE ABOUT THE RIEMANN HYPOTHESIS

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ABSTRACT. In mathematics, the Riemann Hypothesis is a conjecture that the Riemann zeta function has its zeros only at the negative even integers and complex numbers with real part $\frac{1}{2}$. Many consider it to be the most important unsolved problem in pure mathematics. It is one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems selected by the Clay Mathematics Institute to carry a US 1,000,000 prize for the first correct solution. The Robin's inequality consists in $\sigma(n) < e^\gamma \times n \times \ln \ln n$ where $\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function and $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant. The Robin's inequality is true for every natural number $n > 5040$ if and only if the Riemann Hypothesis is true. We demonstrate an interesting result about the smallest possible counterexample of the Robin's inequality exceeding 5040. However, according to this result, the existence of such counterexample seems unlikely. In this way, we provide a new step forward in the efforts of trying to prove the Riemann Hypothesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

$\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function of n [1]:

$$\sum_{d|n} d.$$

Define $s(n)$ to be $\frac{\sigma(n)}{n}$. Say the Robin's inequality is satisfied for n when

$$s(n) < e^\gamma \log \log n.$$

The constant $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant, and \log is the natural logarithm. The importance of this property is: if the Robin's inequality is satisfied for all $n > 5040$, then the Riemann Hypothesis is true [3]. There are several known results about the possible counterexamples of the Robin's inequality exceeding 5040 [1]. In this way, we show that

Theorem 1.1. *Let $n > 5040$ and $n = r \times q$, where q denotes the largest prime factor of n . If $n > 5040$ is the smallest integer such that n does not satisfy the Robin's inequality, then*

$$\frac{1}{\log q} - y - \log y > \log \log n.$$

Here, it is $y = 1 - \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}$.

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2. MATERIALS & METHODS

Here, it is a very useful Lemma:

Lemma 2.1. *Suppose that $n > 5040$ and let $n = r \times q$, where q denotes the largest prime factor of n . We have*

$$s(n) \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right) \times s(r).$$

Proof. Suppose that n is the form of $m \times q^k$ where $q \nmid m$ and m and k are natural numbers. We have that

$$s(n) = s(m \times q^k) = s(m) \times s(q^k)$$

since s is multiplicative and m and q are coprimes [4]. However, we note that

$$s(q^k) \leq s(q^{k-1}) \times s(q)$$

due to we know that $s(a \times b) \leq s(a) \times s(b)$ when $a, b \geq 2$ [4]. In this way, we obtain that

$$s(q^{k-1}) \times s(q) = s(q^{k-1}) \times \left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right)$$

according to the value of $s(q)$ [4]. In addition, we analyze that

$$s(m) \times s(q^{k-1}) = s(m \times q^{k-1}) = s(r)$$

because s is multiplicative and m and q are coprimes [4]. Finally, we obtain that

$$s(n) = s(m) \times s(q^k) \leq s(m) \times s(q^{k-1}) \times s(q) = s(r) \times \left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right)$$

and as a consequence, the proof is finished. \square

3. RESULTS

Theorem 3.1. *Let $n > 5040$ and $n = r \times q$, where q denotes the largest prime factor of n . If $n > 5040$ is the smallest integer such that n does not satisfy the Robin's inequality, then*

$$\frac{1}{\log q} - y - \log y > \log \log n.$$

Here, it is $y = 1 - \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}$.

Proof. Suppose that n is the smallest integer exceeding 5040 that does not satisfy the Robin's inequality. Let $n = r \times q$, where q denotes the largest prime factor of n . In this way, the following inequality

$$s(n) \geq e^\gamma \times \log \log n$$

should be true. We know that

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right) \times s(r) \geq s(q \times r) \geq s(n) \geq e^\gamma \times \log \log n$$

due to Lemma 2.1. Besides, this shows that

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right) \times e^\gamma \times \log \log r > e^\gamma \times \log \log n$$

should be true as well. Certainly, if n is the smallest counterexample of the Robin's inequality exceeding 5040, then the Robin's inequality is satisfied on r [1]. That is the same as

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right) \times \log \log r > \log \log n.$$

We have that

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right) \times \log \log r > \log(\log r + \log q)$$

where we notice that $\log(a + c) = \log a + \log\left(1 + \frac{c}{a}\right)$. This follows

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{q}\right) \times \log \log r > \log \log r + \log\left(1 + \frac{\log q}{\log r}\right)$$

which is equal to

$$(1 + q) \times \log \log r > q \times \log \log r + q \times \log\left(1 + \frac{\log q}{\log r}\right)$$

and thus,

$$\log \log r > q \times \log\left(1 + \frac{\log q}{\log r}\right).$$

This implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\log \log r}{\log\left(1 + \frac{\log q}{\log r}\right)} &= \\ \frac{\log \log r}{\log \frac{\log r + \log q}{\log r}} &= \\ \frac{\log \log r}{\log \frac{\log n}{\log r}} &= \\ \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n - \log \log r} &= \\ \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n \times \left(1 - \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}\right)} &= \\ \frac{\frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}}{\left(1 - \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}\right)} &> q \end{aligned}$$

should be true. If we assume that $y = 1 - \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}$ and using the inequality $1 + x \leq e^x$ [2], then we analyze that

$$\frac{\frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}}{\left(1 - \frac{\log \log r}{\log \log n}\right)} = \frac{1 - y}{y} \leq \frac{e^{-y}}{y}.$$

As result, we have

$$\frac{e^{-y}}{y} > q.$$

From the article reference [4], we know that

$$q > (\log n) \times e^{-\frac{1}{\log q}}.$$

Consequently, we obtain that

$$\frac{e^{\frac{1}{\log q} - y}}{y} > \log n.$$

If we apply the logarithm to the both sides of the previous inequality, then we can see that

$$\frac{1}{\log q} - y - \log y > \log \log n$$

and therefore, the proof is completed. \square

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